

Numerical Analysis of Ballistic Performance of Hybrid Polymer Composites

Aidel Kadum Jassim Al-Shamary*¹, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Diyala University, Diyala, Iraq
Abdul Rahman N. Abed², Department of Mechanical Engineering, Al-Nahrain University, Baghdad, Iraq
Ramazan Karakuzu³, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Dokuz Eylül University, İzmir, Türkiye
*Corresponding author: adel_kadum500@yahoo.com

Abstract

This study represents numerical study to evaluate the ballistic performance of hybrid composite material which consist of S2-glass and Kevlar. Hybrid composite materials were modelled with thickness of 6.5 mm and plane dimensions of 100 x 100 mm for each configuration using LS-DYNA. The structure of specimens has been modelled by six different configurations. Then all specimens were subjected to five different velocities from 453 to 797 m/s. The results show that the largest ballistic velocity limit was achieved for the sample consisting of seventeen layers of S2 glass and six layers of Kevlar.

Keywords: S-glass fabric; Kevlar fabric; Hybrid composite materials; and Finite element analysis

Introduction

The interest in the topic of hybrid composite materials has grown over the past few years because of hybrid composite materials have used in armors system, such as bullet proof body armors, aircraft, and automotive, which should possess high strength, sufficient flexibility, light in weight and also be resistance to penetration. Sen, et al. [1] studied addition shear thickening fluid during manufacturing the Body armors, which are fabricated of several layers of Kevlar fabrics because it has high strength and flexibility. Simulations study was carried out by using different impact velocities of projectiles. The results show that the performance of ballistic test affected by shear thickening fluid (STF) and about 75 % of energy was consumed in the shear thickening fluid materials. Karthick and Ramajeyathilagam [2] used projectile hemispherical nose with 7.52 mm diameter to subject the composite materials to impact angles of high velocity impacts. The effect of stacking sequence, layer and impact angles were studied using finite element analysis by code of LS DYNA. The numerical results show that the thicknesses of target and projectile angle of impact explain the critical contribution on the ballistic resistance of the composite materials. Pham, et al. [3] investigated in the mechanisms of failure fiber after subjecting ballistic impact to specimens of Kevlar numerically. The mechanisms of failure fiber were analyzed. One of yarn consists of around 400 fibers. This model can use in order to develop the micro mesoscopic with multi-scale, model for the Kevlar fabric in the next works. The transverse wave propagation was observed and also time versus velocity of projectile is investigated using tension force for each fiber with the mesoscopic and sub-yarn of level models. Karthick and Ramajeyathilagam [4] investigated utilizing in hybrid composite to study high speed impact numerically by LS DYNA code. E-Glass, Carbon and Kevlar fibers were selected as reinforcement polymer to produce hybrid composites with different stacking sequence. Two types of nosed projectiles hemispherical and cylindrical with same mass and 28 mm and 25.3 mm length respectively, were used in this study. The results were found show that carbon fiber was weak at comparing with Kevlar fiber in the impact test. While, strength of impact is increased at using the hybridization of Kevlar, carbon and Glass fibers in composites materials. Pathak et al. [5] studied improves the performance of ballistic limit for the lightweight of composite materials using Kevlar fiber. the result shows that limit of ballistic increased after addition the alumina with Hybrid composite plates. The main objective of this work focuses on numerically investigating ballistic impact for hybrid composite materials.

Computational model

The numerical analytical of impact tests on the hybrid composite materials was explained in this paper after modelling the target of laminated using woven fabric as plate. Different structure of numerical models was simulated of hybrid composite materials using S-glass and Kevlar. The Woven fabric of numerical models was created using Composite Damage (MAT 022) with 6.5 mm thickness. The model of hybrid composite materials with different number of layers were subjected to high velocity

impact, Table 1 shows designed layers' number of each one of woven fabric hybrid composite numerically.

Table 1. The hybrid specimens by two materials

Hybrid type	Placing				Stacking sequences of materials with 6.5 mm
	Front side	Number of layers	Back side	Number of layers	
case 1	Kevlar	7	S-glass	16	[7 Kevlar/16 S-glass]
case 2	Kevlar	6	S-glass	17	[6 Kevlar/17 S-glass]
case 3	S-glass	16	Kevlar	7	[16 S-glass/7 Kevlar]
case 4	S-glass	17	Kevlar	6	[17 S-glass/6 Kevlar]
case 5	S-glass	16	Kevlar	7	[2 S-glass/1Kevlar/2 S-glass/1Kevlar/2 S-glass/1Kevlar/2 S-glass/1Kevlar/2 S-glass/1Kevlar/2 S-glass/1Kevlar/2 S-glass]
case 6	S-glass	16	Kevlar	7	[4 S-glass/3 Kevlar/4 S-glass/1Kevlar/4 S-glass/3 Kevlar/4 S-glass]

Program of LS-DYNA Ls-Prepost was used to design and solving the model. The specimens of numerical model were designed with dimensions of 100mmx100mm and thickness 6.5 mm using S-glass and Kevlar. Before testing, the specimens were fixed to the test fixture with an active impact zone of 85 mm diameter in the Program of LS-DYNA as illustrated in Figure 1. Additionally, Table 2 illustrates the mechanical properties of hybrid polymer composite materials. However, Table 3 shows the final thicknesses of specimens.

Figure 1. The dimensions of specimen

Table 2. Mechanical properties of polymer composite materials.

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	S-Glass/ Epoxy	Kevlar/ epoxy
Density	ρ	kg/m ³	1750	1117
Elastic Modulus-Longitudinal	E_1	MPa	20256	17230
Elastic Modulus-Transverse	E_2	MPa	30310	17230
Elastic Modulus-Normal	E_3	MPa	15170	10338
Poisson's Ratio	ν_{23}	-	0.11	0.12
Poisson's Ratio	ν_{31}	-	0.11	0.12
Poisson's Ratio	ν_{12}	-	0.17	0.2
Tensile Strength-Longitudinal	X_t	MPa	630	425
Compressive Strength-Longitudinal	X_c	MPa	397	88
Tensile Strength-Transverse	Y_t	MPa	590	425
Compressive Strength-Transverse	Y_c	MPa	426	88
Tensile Strength-Normal	Z_t	MPa	366	255
Compressive Strength-Normal	Z_c	MPa	247	53
Shear Modulus-Transverse	G_{23}	MPa	2580	3306
Shear Modulus-Transverse	G_{31}	MPa	2580	3306
Shear Modulus-In plane	G_{12}	MPa	4300	5510
Shear Strength-Transverse	S_{23}	MPa	60	40
Shear Strength-Transverse	S_{31}	MPa	60	40
Shear Strength-In plane	S_{12}	MPa	99	66

Table 3. The thickness of specimens

Types	Created parameters	Stacking sequences of materials and thickness	
Hybrid	S-glass/Kevlar	3.25 mm S-glass/epoxy	3.25 mm Kevlar/epoxy

While, Material type Rigid Model (MAT_020) was used to design projectile for ballistic penetration impact test. The rigid mode is applied on materials under different high velocity impact with projectile mesh 0.25 mm as illustrated in Figure 2 for ballistic test. Table 4 shows the mechanical properties of steel projectile.

Figure 2. The simulation of projectile.

Table 4. Mechanical properties of steel AISI 4340 projectiles [6]

Modulus of elasticity (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Density (kg/m ³)	Yield stress (MPa)	Tangent modulus (MPa)	Failure strain
200	0.29	7850	970	470	0.77

The model with mixed mesh type at modelling of hybrid composite materials was used as shown in the Figure 3. In the numerical studies were performed by different range of high velocity impact at subjecting the laminates which start from 453 to 797 m/s as illustrated in Table 5 for each type of hybrid polymer composite materials.

Figure 3. Meshing of specimen

Table 5. High velocity impact types of hybrid composite

Test number	1	2	3	4	5
Impact velocity (m/s)	453	490	627	702	797

MAT 22 failure model relations are given below:

Longitudinal tension:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_t}\right)^2 + \bar{\tau} > 1, \quad \sigma_1 > 0 \quad (1)$$

Transverse tension:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_t}\right) + \bar{\tau} > 1, \quad \sigma_2 > 0 \quad (2)$$

Transverse compression:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{2S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{Y_c}{2S_{12}}\right)^2 - 1\right]\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_c}\right) + \bar{\tau} > 1, \quad \sigma_2 < 0 \quad (3)$$

where σ_1 and σ_2 represent stresses in longitudinal and transverse direction respectively. X_t and Y_t are tensile strengths in longitudinal and transverse directions respectively. X_c and Y_c are compressive strengths in longitudinal and transverse direction, respectively. S_{12} represents shear strength in 1-2 plane.

$$\bar{\tau} = \frac{\frac{\tau_{12}^2}{2G_{12}} + \frac{3}{4} \alpha \tau_{12}^4}{\frac{S_{12}^2}{2G_{12}} + \frac{3}{4} \alpha \tau_{12}^4} \quad (4)$$

where τ_{12} is shear stress in 1-2 plane, G_{12} is shear modulus in 1-2 plane, α is coefficient of nonlinear shear stress-shear strain relation. In MAT 22 model, α coefficient was assumed as zero.

Results and Discussion

The structure of specimens has been modelled by six different types combinations than all specimens were subjected by five different velocities. The Curves of fitting residual velocity-impact velocity data are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Curve fitting residual velocity-impact velocity data for hybrid composites S-glass/Kevlar

Ballistic limit velocity and the parameter *a* [6] were obtained from Eq. (5) curve fitting residual velocity-impact velocity data in Excel as shown in Figure 4. A straight line is fitted from the data obtained by squaring both sides of Eq. (5).

The curve fit's correlation coefficient (R²) was > 0.9, which is considered as a very good fit [7]. Ballistic limit velocity and parameter *a* are given in Table 6 for each type. As can be shown from Table 6 and Figure 5, the structure of specimen with 17 layers S-glass and 6 layers of Kevlar has larger ballistic limit velocity than other structures of hybrid specimens numerically, however Table 7 explains residual velocity for all types and at each impact velocity. Curves of residual velocity with impact velocity data of S2-glass/Kevlar hybrid composites materials were shown in Figure 6, the curves are consistent with each other.

$$v_r = a (v_i^2 - v_{bl}^2)^{1/2}, \text{ for } a < 1 \tag{5}$$

Table 6. Configurations and ballistic velocity limits (V_{bl}) of hybrid composites with parameters *a*

Case	Structure of specimen	<i>a</i>	V _{bl} (m/s)
1	7 Kevlar / 16 S-glass	0.823	254
2	6 Kevlar / 17 S-glass	0.817	271
3	16 S-glass / 7 Kevlar	0.802	259
4	17 S-glass / 6 Kevlar	0.824	275
5	2 S-glass/ 1Kevlar/2 S-glass/1 Kevlar/2 S-glass/ 1Kevlar/2 S-glass/1 Kevlar /2 S-glass/1 Kevlar/ 2 S-glass/ 1Kevlar/2 S-glass/ 1 Kevlar/2 S-glass	0.802	261
6	4 S-glass/3 Kevlar/4 S-glass/1Kevlar/4 S-glass/3 Kevlar/4 S-glass	0.802	261

Figure 5. Ballistic limit velocities of hybrid composites S-glass/Kevlar

Table 7. Ballistic results of hybrid composite using S-glass/Kevlar materials

Case-1			Case-2			Case-3		
Tests	Impact velocity (m/s)	Numerical Residual velocity (m/s)	Tests	Impact velocity (m/s)	Numerical Residual velocity (m/s)	Tests	Impact velocity (m/s)	Numerical Residual velocity (m/s)
1	453	300	1	453	300	1	453	300
2	490	331	2	490	331	2	490	331
3	627	459	3	627	463	3	627	462
4	702	520	4	702	527	4	702	519
5	797	606	5	797	614	5	797	606

Case-4			Case-5			Case-6		
Tests	Impact velocity (m/s)	Numerical Residual velocity (m/s)	Tests	Impact velocity (m/s)	Numerical Residual velocity (m/s)	Tests	Impact velocity (m/s)	Numerical Residual velocity (m/s)
1	453	300	1	453	299	1	453	299
2	490	332	2	490	329	2	490	329
3	627	463	3	627	461	3	627	461
4	702	533	4	702	518	4	702	518
5	797	617	5	797	605	5	797	605

Figure 6. Numerical residual velocity versus impact velocity diagrams for hybrid composites S-glass/Kevlar

Conclusion

Ballistic impact tests were carried out on all the specimens of hybrid composites materials which have 100 mm square dimensions with 6.5 mm thickness and different structure of specimen using LS-DYNA LS-PREPOST after modelling the target of laminated using woven fabric (S-glass and Kevlar) in plate numerically, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Impact velocity corresponding to zero residual velocity gives ballistic limit velocity which is different for each structure of polymer composite materials at same thickness.
- The ballistic limit velocity for hybrid composite which consists of seventeen layers of S2-glass and six layers of Kevlar is higher ballistic limit velocity when comparing between different structure of hybrid composite which consist of two materials.

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